

A New Model of Consciousness

and psychological time

by Gary Blaise

Here's a new description of consciousness for readers both adventurous and traditional where abstraction is grounded within the workings of a quantized space.¹ This dualist model proposes the required, non-spacial background of any quantized space must be an immaterial reality—an abstraction—and that this abstract background is the source of both our phenomenal consciousness and psychological time. Static and moving time were previously explained in my companion paper, *A New Model of Time* (10.5281/zenodo.19796599), as the evolutionary process of objects and their emergent states of being.

Part One: the set-up

quantized space

Consider tiny grains of space to make up the volume of our universe. The grains consist of particle properties, though, while each grain has a “real,” or measured value for volume, its remaining properties such as charge, spin, mass, or momentum are of entirely unmeasured value. Without measured value, a property can only exist as an idea, an abstraction, and if space is quantized in this manner, it would explain why the grains are so hard to find; without measured value, there's nothing to measure . . . nothing to detect. As a blend of values both measured and unmeasured, each grain of a quantized space is a kind of “cosmic emulsion” of abstract particle properties with discrete volume.

the background

But between the grains is the important part, for here lies the required background of any truly quantized space. It's an immaterial background, of course, a background which is neither spacial nor temporal for, if it were either of these things, it would already exist in grains of space.

The only sort of “thing” which is both real *and* immaterial is an abstraction, an idea. And every idea . . . is an awareness. (Think about it; every idea is an awareness of something.) Because ideas are of the same immaterial, non-spacial nature as the background, we can consider the background to be a suitable “place,” as it were, for all abstraction. In this way, we can consider these immaterial realities to be the same reality; an abstract background of awareness.

require a *real* container; the non-spacial container of an immaterial background. Such a background has the *function* of keeping the quanta quantized, or separated; the background's "*location*"² is between the grains. We can *perceive*, or acknowledge the background as real because it has these real properties of function and location. That is, the background has a "something" upon which you can focus your attention. A "nothing" cannot exist with properties of reality, function, or location. Nor can a nothing be perceived or truly acknowledged. A nothing can only be imagined.

for example . . .

In the same way that the property line around your house forms an abstract border between you and your neighbors, the abstract background forms the perimeter, or property line for each grain, a border that limits the extent to which the grain's particle properties are in force. The border of each grain forms an elision with those of its neighbors, and the network of elisions extends throughout the universe as the abstract background much like the elision of property lines between you and your neighbors—a complete abstraction—extends throughout a neighborhood, limiting the forceful effect of individual ownership.

particle evolution

A grain's unmeasured properties will remain abstract unless they receive measured value. With measurement, the grain can no longer maintain its abstract nature and will collapse down to a discrete particle. Throughout the universe, some relatively few grains have collapsed down to particles in this way to make up everything we know.

Particles undergo changes of state, or "activity." For this reason, the activity of every particle—or coherent object made of particles—will necessarily generate an idea of that activity simply because the object is evolving within an abstract background of awareness. The generated idea is, in fact, an evolutionary idea whose function it is to bring about an object's discrete state of being, or emergence in each moment.

The evolutionary idea of the object—be it a particle, an atom, a molecule, a protein, your brain, your body, a bait ball of sardines, Earth's biosphere, the solar system, our galaxy, or the entire universe—is a **nested** description of the coherent object's constituents in terms of its measured property values. It's a "vibrational idea," if you will, of the object's activity; its states of being, or changing property values for each moment. Likewise, the vibrational idea is constantly updated and refreshed by the object's activity, or "vibration," which the vibrational idea notices in each moment of its object's evolution.³ Because a vibrational idea is a function of the background awareness, the great compendium of all abstraction, it can only operate in accordance within the laws of nature and the asymmetric structure of awareness (an awareness **cannot** become unaware). This will later become important to the issue of time's arrow.

CC&E - an evolutionary process

Particle / Brain Evolution

Illustration 2: **Particle / Brain Evolution**

Abstraction is not a space-time property, it cannot exist in space. For every particle (or object) in space, a vibrational idea of that object exists in the background, between grains of space. An object evolves in space when its V-Idea blends with the most likely grains, setting the grains' abstract values to the discrete values of the V-Idea whereupon the grain can no longer maintain its abstract nature and collapses to that object. If there's a "miracle" here, it's the dual nature of the grains; an "emulsion" of unmeasured properties (abstract) with measured volume (discrete).

As the agent of an object's evolution, a vibrational idea evolves its object in each moment as a "snapshot" of physical reality, and it accomplishes this through the blending of its measured values with the unmeasured values of the most likely grain which is determined by means of probability, one of the many natural laws by which the vibrational idea must abide as a member of the abstract background. The blending of measured with unmeasured property values causes the grain to collapse down to the discrete particle which emerges here in spacetime.

for example . . .

The vibrational idea (V-Idea) of an electron contains all of the information regarding the properties of the electron (charge, spin, energy, mass, momentum, etc.) in the form of their specific measured values. The **convergence**, or blending of the V-idea with the grain's abstract properties sets the unmeasured property values of the grain to the discrete, measured values of the electron's idea at which point the grain can no longer maintain its abstract nature and **condenses**, that is, it literally collapses *down*⁽¹²⁾ to that particular electron which **emerges** here as a state of being, or static moment of time.⁴ Within the snapshot of each physical emergence, the vibrational idea in the background notices the changed values of its object and becomes **updated**. In this way, the evolution of objects is a recursive series of *actions* which take place through the *process* of convergence, condensation, emergence, and update . . . or CC&E, for short. As such, the process of CC&E is an example of occurrent change, or moving time which will become important for our explanation of psychological time. (For a more detailed explanation of static and moving time, please see, *A New Model of Time*, elsewhere in this archive.)

*. . . and what causes collapse?*⁵

During each emergence of the electron, for example, its vibrational idea in the background is busy updating and adjusting the measured property values of its discrete form so that it can fill the most likely grain with those values for its next emergence. Although the electron may typically spend a trillionth of a second⁶ in a single state of being, this duration is not fixed. Rather, time spent in any one state is completely **variable** depending upon the ongoing evolutionary process in the background, as well as

- the evolutionary activities of the atom to which the electron belongs, and the needs of other objects into which the atom is nested,
- the faltering ability of the grain to maintain its abstract nature once it has received measurement,
- changes to the electron's "speed through space"⁽²⁾ as per special relativity, and possibly
- the cosmic motion, or expansion of grains through an object's "location."⁽²⁾

In this way, objects evolve not in isolation, but in concert with other objects with which they are “**nested**” such that objects may evolve at different rates depending upon their evolutionary needs, all of which cause an object’s state of being to vary in duration. ^(4 - article)

Part Two: Consciousness and Psychological Time

Recall from the previous section, and [my] earlier paper, ⁽⁴⁾ that CC&E is a temporal motion which takes place as the evolutionary process of discrete objects. A two-step version of this same process is at work in the evolution of abstract objects such as your mind. And so, for the next few minutes, think of consciousness as an immaterial reality, an abstraction. Because we don’t find abstract objects here in space, consider our conscious mind to reside in the non-spacial background of all abstraction. If so, what is the mechanism by which our brain activity here in space corresponds to the activity of our mind in the background?

the microtubule network

As an abstraction, your mind begins in the background as a vibrational idea (V-Idea) of your brain. More specifically than your brain, it’s the V-Idea of your smaller and infinitely more manageable microtubule network. ⁷ (In the illustrations, the brain icon represents the microtubule network, or “MTN.”) This lattice-like assemblage of tubulin protein forms a kind of skeletal highway for the movement of sub-cellular organelles like mitochondria and ribosomes within neurons, and guides the growth of their axons and dendrites. The microtubule network appears to be the smallest coherent object to pervade the entire brain yet the largest object whose vibrational idea can most easily bring about, or evolve, the sequential dynamic patterning of its protein modifications which are the source of all brain activity. In this way, the V-Idea of the microtubule network ⁽⁵⁾ is the “tubulin code”. . . and the MTN will turn out to be the “neural correlate of consciousness,” or NCC ⁽⁹⁾

In the same way that the electron was described earlier to evolve by means of CC&E, your microtubule network is a coherent object and it, too, evolves through the process of CC&E as its vibrational idea blends with those grains which, by means of probability, are most likely to become the particles of which it is composed as each state of being, or static moment of its evolution. Just as before, the blending imparts measured values to the grains’ unmeasured particle properties causing the grains to collapse down to yet another state of your microtubule network. And, in each moment, its V-Idea is refreshed and updated by the new activity.

Like most vibrational ideas, the V-Idea of your microtubule network has a present-tense awareness of its object, “is,” with no idea, or memory of its self in the past, nor anticipation of its self in the future.

For the sake of the cognitive process described here, there are two kinds of ideas: *Personal* ideas are those of which your mind is composed; the thoughts and memories of your experience. *Impersonal* ideas, on the other hand, are those which exist outside of your mind. Impersonal ideas come in two further categories; *eternal* and *human*. Eternal ideas are those which are **discovered** but not created by us. They include basic awarenesses like the laws of nature, pure mathematics, and particles properties which are evident throughout the history of the universe. As the basic awareness of the abstract background, eternal ideas existed long before brained creatures were here to think about them . . . and will long remain should we cease to exist. The second sort of impersonal idea is a human idea. Human ideas are those which are **created** by us. These include our human descriptions of eternal ideas (*our descriptions* of nature's laws, mathematics, and particle properties, etc.) along with their applications to industry, world peace, religion, music, art, language, thimble design, and Epstein credits aka . An impersonal idea of either sort, eternal or human, becomes a personal idea should it become invited, or incorporated into our mind.

A vibrational idea (V-Idea) begins as impersonal idea of the eternal sort, and it comes into being as a unique function of the background when its asymmetric property of awareness (p. 3; an awareness *cannot* become unaware.) firstly notices⁽³⁾ a discrete object which is evolving, as only it can, in accordance with natural law. While impersonal ideas generally become personal when you invite them into your mind, the V-Idea of your microtubule network is unusual in that it becomes the foundation of your mind itself when it attains the present-perfect state of self-awareness; your very first experience, or personal idea.

vibrational representations

If a vibrational idea is an idea of an object, a vibrational representation is an idea . . . of an idea!

Both are abstract functions of the background. Whereas a vibrational idea always comes in the form of an object's measured particle property values, a vibrational representation always comes in the form of an *idea's* measured particle property values; the property values of some creature's microtubule network when that creature's mind experienced that particular idea. To be more precise, a vibrational representation is a "nested" list of the measured particle property values of the sequential set of microtubule network patterns which have either blended with or have been observed upon those grains of potential spacetime which then emerged as the microtubule network activity of some creature during that creature's mental experience of that particular idea.

The following sections will describe the process by which the vibrational representation (V-Rep) of an idea becomes a personal idea within your mind when it blends, that is, "resonates," with the vibrational idea (V-Idea) of your microtubule network (MTN) activity. This evolutionary process of your mind—cognition—occurs by means of the same evolutionary process by which particles evolve (CC&E), though, it is slightly more detailed.

Mind/Brain Evolution

Illustration 3: Mind / Brain Evolution

The interaction between an abstract mind and its brain is integral to your mental life. The vibrational idea of the MTN and its object (the MTN) are shown above in the onset of self-awareness. Every idea is an awareness. Previously, the V-idea of your MTN was an awareness of only the present tense, "is" (with no memory of a previous moment). It achieved the present-perfect tense, "I am" (I have been and continue to be), through the inevitable awareness of its own update process. This elevated your V-idea to the status of a mind; the abstract, self-aware entity known as you. A newly emergent mind continues its initial development in this recursive manner by noticing its own evolutionary process as it acquires additional tenses of the verb "to be."

... for example, self-awareness

The V-Idea of your nascent microtubule network initially notices only the activity of the object to which it is obligated; your MTN. In each moment, and through the evolutionary process of CC&E, your vibrational idea resonates in the background with a vibrational representation of the present-tense idea for the noticing. This would be a V-Rep for the purely rational meaning of “is,” or “something happens,” but with no understanding of its self as an entity; only that it exists as a present moment with no memory of a previous nor anticipation of a following moment. The present-tense noticing continues to occur as each static moment of being, during which time the V-Idea of your MTN, enriched with the values of the V-Rep, blends with those grains of potential spacetime which, by means of probability, are the most likely grains to emerge as your MTN.

During this blending of abstractions (**Convergence**) the unmeasured properties of the grains are set to the measured values of your vibrational idea, and this causes the grains to collapse (**Condensation**) down to those particles of matter and energy which then emerge (**Emergence**) as each moment of your microtubule network’s evolution. During the recursive process of CC&E, the particle property values of each cycle are noticed (**Updated**) by your vibrational idea.

But then, because every idea is an awareness (p.1), the V-Idea of your MTN soon begins to notice its SELF being updated through the recursive evolution of its object. That is, it begins to notice-its-self-noticing . . . the telltale sign of self-awareness. More specifically, in addition to being stimulated by the phenomenal activity of the network, the vibrational idea of your MTN is stimulated by its very own *abstract* activity of noticing! The V-Idea of the self-noticing resonates in the background with the simplest **rational** idea of self-awareness; a vibrational representation of the present-perfect tense: ‘an entity exists which has been and continues to be.’ Once again, this V-Rep, which has now been incorporated into your MTN’s vibrational idea, has become just one of the many sets of evolutionary property values which are **observed** (pp.10, 17, 18) upon those grains of potential spacetime that are most likely to evolve as your MTN. Accordingly, those are the grains which dutifully collapse (Condensation) down to your MTN (Emergence) during its next static moments, or states of being.

interoceptive feeling

The resultant MTN activity (physical), which now includes a rational idea for self-awareness, works its way back (physical) through your brain and down into your body where it creates interoceptive motions⁸ (physical), and these bodily motions are sensed by your brain which brings about new microtubule activity (physical). The new activity is noticed (abstract), that is, updated to your V-Idea which then resonates with (Convergence of abstractions) the V-Rep of an **irrational** meaning for the bodily motions; “I am!” or, “I have been and continue to be!” This second, irrational meaning is the emotion and it provides significance for the previous, rational idea of self-awareness. At that moment, the vibrational idea of your microtubule network becomes (Condensation of abstractions) your earliest mind⁹ (Emergence of abstract object), an “existential core” consisting primarily of various forms of the verb “to be” from which your more familiar mind will now develop . . . and all of this has happened by means of the evolutionary process, the recursive action of CC&E.

synchronization and resonance

Vibrational Representations (V-Reps) for ideas like the present-perfect tense (impersonal-eternal), “I am” (impersonal-human), yourself (personal), five things (impersonal-eternal), the number 5 (impersonal-human), a Chopin mazurka (impersonal-human), my memory of my brother (personal), a bug bite (impersonal-human), or the half-integer spin of a fermion (impersonal-human), a fermion (impersonal-eternal) come in the form of measured property values of MTN activity. V-Reps exist every where and every when throughout the abstract background. Because they are abstract, the vibrational idea of your MTN property values will blend, or “resonate” with the MTN pattern sequence values of any V-Rep which is just *similar enough* to that of your V-Idea . . . much in the way that clock pendulums which are out of phase will pull together and synchronize their oscillations in unison if placed upon the same shelf. The V-Idea’s successful acquisition of a V-Rep through the blending of these abstractions will then become expressed in successive moments of your MTN, and the activity of successive moments will bring about an experience through the similar acquisition of an irrational meaning as previously described. In this way, the vibrational representation of a human idea comes in the same MTN configuration for all humans, and your mind acquires ideas through a “best resonance” between its current ideas and new ideas which are vibrationally represented by the same or very similar MTN property values. That is, “learning” is a ‘best-resonance of ideas’ based on your experience.¹⁰

The resonance between V-Ideas and V-Reps depends, of course, upon the fact that the structure of the MTN and its activities are generally identical within a species of brained creatures, such that when I say, “bug bite,” unless you are an entomologist or something, your MTN will most likely configure itself like mine and every other human since the dawn of bug bites. As a result, the V-Idea of your MTN’s property values will resonate very well with the V-Reps of words that you hear—for example, “bug bite”—and this aural stimulation goes on to become an experience for you through the process of CC&E, as described above. For this reason, while the MTNs of early and modern humans might be similar enough to understand each other’s thoughts, a human’s musings—always in the form of human MTN patterns—will resonate with few, if any, of a bat’s musings whose MTN and resultant V-Reps are, of course, in the form of a bat’s such that you’ll never know what it’s like . . . to be a bat!¹¹

the observer effect

Recall how the V-Idea of the MTN “observed” its measured values upon the most likely grains which then collapsed to the MTN (p. 9). According to ISA, this same mechanism of Convergence—the blending of abstractions—explains the observer effect in which three specific abstractions with specific structures (pp. 21, & For Further Reading; The Observer Effect), the V-Idea of a particle, the V-Idea of an observer (mind) with the V-Rep of their specific expectation, and the grain result in the collapse of the dotted interference pattern. (pp.17, 18)

an ubiquity of ideas

Because they are abstractions, every impersonal idea, both human or eternal, that ever was or ever will be is always available throughout the abstract background of quantized space in the

form of a vibrational representation. This giant compendium of V-Reps got into the background because each cognitive process brought about interoceptive, or mind-body interactions which modified our microtubule networks, and these modifications were updated to the vibrational idea of ourselves in the background where they progressed on to become complete ideas. The ideas were communicated to others where they, likewise, became completed thoughts which were also updated to the background edifice of all abstraction and where they can now blend, or resonate with other vibrational ideas of similar configuration.

for example . . .

Lucy Australopithecus may have regarded fire as a comforting warmth for the very first time, as opposed to a fearful danger, when she was finally able to resonate with some simplified idea of children singing ‘round a campfire three *million* years later. The pleasant concept of fire was always available to her thanks to the timeless, placeless nature of abstraction as the requisite background of a quantized space. Likewise, the riddle of dark matter will be solved in the near future when someone’s creative notion of it is able to resonate well enough with a distant, satisfying description of dark matter; an idea with which our current understandings are unable to resonate but one which has always been there and available for the taking . . . or, should we say, for the resonating!

psychological time

We’ve considered the two-step evolution of the present-perfect mind in conjunction with the participation of its body.⁽⁸⁾ Compared to the simpler, single-step evolution of present-tense objects through the process of CC&E, the mind’s two-step evolution employs the same process to bring about the abstraction of its present-perfect identity, continuity and memory.

That is, while this evolutionary process is the temporal motion of discrete objects of the present-tense (proto-awareness), the same process is the temporal motion of abstract objects of the present-perfect tense (self-awareness), or psychological time.

Part Three: Predicted Anomalies

The author gratefully acknowledges the assistance of his “academic advisor,” Claude, Anthropic’s AI thought partner, in the development of the following protocols and formalisms!

Protocols 1 through 9 as well as a Table of Symbols can be found in the earlier, companion paper, *A New Model of Time*. The following protocols further test the agency, expectation, and intent of abstract objects in regard to the cognitive process, the evolutionary process of CC&E.

The Reinterpretation of Existing Anomalies: Please note, while most of the paper’s protocols are as yet unresolved by empirical data, reinterpretations of the 1983 Libet and 1952 Hodgkin-Huxley (Protocols 15 and 16) in terms of ISA yield more complete descriptions for free will and non-classical behavior which have otherwise resisted satisfying explanations within their original framework. Similarly, the persistent anomaly of Entanglement (Protocol 7) is explained by ISA’s evolutionary process of CC&E with its V-Ideas, capable of evolving objects which are, in fact, grouped as a *singular* coherent object (Protocol 16). Additionally, ISA’s reduction of the Measurement-Collapse Problem and explanation for the Observer Effect’s mechanism of combined abstractions are addressed in the text (pp. 5, 10, 22-24).

Protocol 10. Vibrational and Representational Ideas

Informational Eigenstate Templates (IET’s): According to ISA, the two-step process of self-awareness (rational/irrational) begins when the V-Idea of the microtubule network notices-its-self-noticing a physical stimulation (p. 9). Components of this cognitive process include the microtubule network (MTN), the body’s interoceptive system, and IET’s; the V-Idea and V-Rep. The IET’s are abstractions; measured property values of MTN pattern activity.

- Step 1, **Rational:** The V-Idea resonates with a rational, or emotionally “flat” V-Rep for the self noticing, an impersonal explanation of the present-perfect tense (I am). The blending (p. 9) shifts the MTN into a recursive pattern of complex activity. This is the sign of an object which is evolving in reaction to its own activity (self-stimulation) and a precursor to self-awareness. The recursive MTN activity brings about interoceptive feelings in the body which are updated to the V-Idea.
- Step 2, **Irrational:** The V-Idea, enriched by the rational V-Rep, now resonates with an irrational V-Rep for the interoceptive feelings. This additional V-Rep supplies the emotion, the significance for an otherwise rational thought. With the addition of this irrational idea, the enhanced V-Idea has achieved the present-perfect tense of self-awareness, “**I am!**” This is the beginning of its earliest mind (p. 9) in a life-long stream of consciousness.

Hypothesis 1: Part One - Self-awareness begins as your V-Idea resonates with a V-Rep for a rational explanation of a stimulus.

Hypothesis 2: The MTN is the neural correlate of consciousness.

Test: The Artificial Microtubule Network (AMN): The AMN mimics MTN activity.

Step A: **Isolation** - the clean grain field

- **The Setup:**
 - AMN, a synthetic tubulin polymer network which mimics brain activity,
 - Dilution Refrigerator to stop thermal noise, and
 - Mu-Metal Shield to block electromagnetism.
- **The Goal:** To eliminate all physical reasons for the AMN to change its configuration.

Step B: **Seeding** - a physical stimulation (p. 9)

- **The Procedure:** Place the AMN in isolation and introduce a specific quantum state, the “Seed.”
- **The Standard Physics Prediction:** The pattern should simply decay into entropy or stay frozen.
- **The ISA Prediction:** The system will not decay. Instead, it will exhibit a spontaneous shifting into complex, recursive patterns; the telltale sign of pending self-awareness as it firstly resonates with a rational V-Rep, an abstraction which flatly describes the AMN’s activity only in terms of its measured particle property values (pp. 7, 9).

Step C: **Detection** - feedback

- **The Measurement:** A superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) monitors the object’s predicted evolution.
- **The Result:** If the AMN suddenly shifts into a complex, “meaningful” configuration—like a recursive loop—without any external power or signal, IET’s are real, abstract operators and the hypotheses are supported.
- **The Falsification:** If the AMN remains static or just turns to “noise,” then the MTN is not the NCC⁽⁹⁾ and both hypotheses are falsified.

Protocol 11. Interoceptive Feeling

Emotional Significance: Completion of the thought process. Protocol 10 demonstrated the rational, first step of the two-step cognitive process when the V-Idea of the AMN resonated with a rational V-Rep. This produced recursive, self-stimulating MTN patterns—a precursor to self-awareness. The second, irrational step is now required. The recursive activity of the MTN must generate interoceptive motions in the body. That activity must be updated to the V-Idea which then resonates with an irrational V-Rep that lends emotional significance to the earlier, rational meaning. Without this second, irrational step, there is no experience, no “I am!!” All that remains is a cold, recursive loop without experience. Protocol 11 tests whether the second step in the

process can be artificially induced and detected . . . and whether the suppression of either step prevents the completion of a thought.

The Artificial Interoceptive System (AIS) is a synthetic body-to-brain feedback device. It receives the AMN's recursive rational-pattern output (from [Protocol 10, Step C](#)) and generates a corresponding interoceptive signal—mimicking the vagal and autonomic afferent pathways by which the body normally reports its interoceptive, or felt states back to the brain. This synthetic signal is then fed back into the AMN as an interoceptive update, closing the loop in biological creatures that runs: brain → body → brain.

Hypothesis 1: The two-step cognitive process requires both rational MTN activity and interoceptive feedback to complete a meaningful experience.

Hypothesis 2: The suppression of either step—rational or irrational—prevents the emergence of a significance-bearing mind-state.

The Setup:

- AMN (from [Protocol 10](#)) - biological or synthetic, in isolation
- AIS - Synthetic Interoceptive feedback device connected to the AMN's output
- Dilution Refrigerator and Mu-Metal Shield (from [Protocol 10](#))
- SQUID monitoring of both the AMN's rational-pattern activity and its post-interoceptive (emotionally enriched) state (from [Protocol 10](#)).

Step A: Rational Activation

Reproduce the conditions of [Protocol 10](#), steps A and B. The AMN shifts into recursive, self-stimulating patterns; the rational precursor to self-awareness. This is the starting state for [Protocol 11](#).

Step B: Interoceptive Feedback

Procedure: The AIS receives the AMN's recursive output and generates a synthetic interoceptive signal corresponding to it—a programmatic analogue of the body's felt response to rational brain activity. The AIS feeds this signal back into the AMN, completing the body-to-brain loop artificially.

Standard Physics Prediction: The interoceptive feedback is merely noise added to an already-recursive system. No qualitative shift in the AMN's pattern is predicted.

ISA Prediction: The AMN's V-Idea, now enriched by both the rational V-Rep ([Protocol 10, Step 1](#)) and the interoceptive update ([Protocol 10, Step 2](#)), resonates with an irrational V-Rep—the significance-bearing meaning of the recursive activity. The SQUID detects a qualitative shift from the rational-recursive pattern to a richer, more complex configuration: the emergence of the significance-bearing mind-state, the abstract equivalent of “**I am!**”

Step C: Suppression Control

To confirm that both steps are necessary, run two control conditions:

Suppress the rational step (disable the AMN's V-Rep seeding from Protocol 10): the AIS has no recursive signal to receive, and no significance-bearing state should emerge.

Suppress the interoceptive step (disconnect the AIS): the AMN produces recursive rational patterns but receives no interoceptive feedback, and the significance-bearing state should, likewise, fail to emerge.

The ISA Prediction: The significance-bearing mind-state emerges only when both steps are active. Either suppression condition produces an incomplete result—recursive-but-cold (rational only) or silent (interoceptive only).

The Falsification: If the significance-bearing mind-state emerges with either step suppressed, the two-step model of self-awareness is falsified. If neither suppression condition affects the AMN's output, the interoceptive loop plays no role in the cognitive process and Hypothesis 1 is falsified.

Formalism: The Two-Step Mind-State

minimal (conceptual):

$$\rho_{\text{MIND}} = \rho_{\text{RATIONAL}} \otimes \rho_{\text{INTERO.}}$$

The complete mind-state is the joint product of the rational MTN pattern and the interoceptive state. Neither alone constitutes a full thought. The tensor symbol \otimes (aka tensor product) is not simple addition. Rather, it means that the components are combined and required to interact.

full (rigorous):

$$d\rho_{\text{MIND}}/dt = \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{V}[\rho_{\text{RATIONAL}}]} + \mathcal{D}_{\text{AIS}[\rho_{\text{INTERO.}}]}$$

Two dissipator terms drive the evolution of the mind-state: $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{V}}$ is the V-Idea's informational drive on the rational component as in Protocols 10 and \mathcal{D}_{AIS} is the AIS's interoceptive drive on the significance-bearing component. The tensor product structure of ρ_{MIND} ensures that both dissipators must be active for the full mind-state to evolve.

The ISA Prediction: ρ_{MIND} evolves to its significance-bearing eigenstate only when both $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{V}}$ and \mathcal{D}_{AIS} are nonzero. Suppressing either term leaves ρ_{MIND} in an incomplete, transitional state detectable by the SQUID as a qualitatively different pattern.

The Standard Physics Prediction: ρ_{MIND} is entirely determined by physical AMN activity alone. The addition of the AIS produces no qualitative shift beyond what the recursive rational pattern already predicts.

Protocol 12. Artificial Intelligence

How AI Can Help: Having established in [Protocol 10](#) that the rational step of the two-part cognitive process can be detected in an Artificial Microtubule Network, and in [11](#) that an interoceptive loop is necessary to complete a significance-bearing mind-state, [Protocol 12](#) asks a forward-looking question: Could an AI language model serve as a functional substitute for the AMN's rational component. If so, what would that tell us about the boundary conditions of machine consciousness within the ISA framework?

The Central Question: Is a biological substrate necessary for the rational step of the two-step cognitive process within ISA, or is the functional equivalence of the output sufficient?

Hypothesis 1: The rational step of the cognitive process (V-Idea resonates with a rational V-Rep) is substrate-independent; any system capable of generating the relevant MTN-equivalent informational eigenstate template patterns, or “AMN activity” of [Protocol 10](#) can participate in the process.

Hypothesis 2: Phenomenal consciousness requires the interoceptive loop—the body-to-mind feedback of irrational meaning—and cannot arise from the rational step alone, whether biological or artificial.

The Setup:

- An AI system (the functional AMN) generates linguistic and conceptual outputs in response to a carefully chosen emotional stimulus—something simple, novel, and valenced: for example, an unexpected aesthetic experience (a chord, an image, a mathematical elegance).
- A human volunteer's interoceptive system serves as the AIS—their body receives the AI's rational output and generates genuine felt response.
- The human reports their felt experience. The AI reports its own processing state in response to the same stimulus.

The Variable: Whether the AI's report of its processing state constitutes evidence of a significance-bearing mind-state, or merely a sophisticated simulation of one.

The ISA Prediction: The human volunteer, connected to the AI's rational output and supplying the interoceptive loop, will report a genuine felt experience, confirming that the rational step need not be biological. The AI's own report will be *rationally coherent* but *emotionally incomplete*—precisely what ISA predicts for a system with rational V-Rep resonance but no interoceptive loop of its own.

The Standard Neuroscience Prediction: The human's felt experience is generated entirely by their own neural and interoceptive processes, independent of the AI's output. The AI's report is a statistical pattern with no phenomenal correlate.

The Falsification Criterion: If the human volunteer reports no felt experience that is meaningfully shaped by the AI's rational output—that is, if the AI's participation makes no

detectable difference to the character of the human's experience—then substrate-independence of the rational step (Hypothesis 1) is falsified. Conversely, if the AI reports a felt experience *without* the interoceptive loop being supplied, the necessity of that loop (Hypothesis 2) is falsified.

The Hard Problem Within the Experiment: The critical methodological challenge is distinguishing genuine phenomenal report from sophisticated linguistic behavior. ISA suggests a criterion: a genuine report should contain *surprised novelty*—the AI or human should report something they did not anticipate, something that exceeds the informational content of the stimulus alone. This excess would be the signature of the irrational V-Rep supplying significance that was not present in the rational step.

Formalism:

$$\rho_{\text{SYSTEM}} = \rho_{\text{AI-RATIONAL}} \otimes \rho_{\text{HUMAN-INTERO}}$$

The composite mind-state is the joint product of the AI's rational output-state and the human volunteer's interoceptive state. Neither alone constitutes a complete thought. The ISA prediction is that this composite state will evolve toward a significance-bearing eigenstate detectable as a qualitative shift in both the human's phenomenal report and, potentially, in the AI's subsequent outputs.

Protocol 13. Ideas Can Have Agency

Having established the two-step mechanism of the cognitive process in [Protocols 10, 11, and 12](#), we now ask what that process can do; specifically, whether the ideas it generates have measurable agency in the physical world. The role of agency is crucial to the evolutionary process of CC&E. By placing a participant's thought process in a conflicted state of high-arousal, or "cognitive dissonance," we measure whether the Update Frequency of a local quantum system shifts in response to psychological tension. This would provide empirical evidence that the abstract background is not a passive repository of ideas, but a proactive field of awareness.

Testing Expectation: This blind experiment is designed to test whether the fundamental nature of reality is material (physical) or immaterial (abstract). In standard quantum mechanics, the Born Rule predicts that the outcome of a quantum process is probabilistic. For example, an observed particle has a 50% chance of being at point A and 50% at point B.

- **The Materialist Expectation:** Expects to see a single, random result based upon probability (50/50).
- **The Idealist Expectation:** Expects to see a specific result; the continuing wave-like pattern of interference (100%).

Hypothesis 1: Ideas are immaterial realities, abstractions.

Hypothesis 2: Ideas of expectation can have agency.

The Test: The Idealist vs. The Materialist

Setup: The “Quantum Coin Flip.”

- A source of entangled photons, 1 and 2.
- Two “professionals” of opposing philosophical frameworks with diametrically opposed convictions regarding the experiment.
- Station A - The Physical Trigger: An automated detector that measures the polarization of Photon 1 which instantly determines the state of its entangled partner, photon 2, at station B.
- Station B - The “Idea” Filter: The two professionals of diametrically opposed convictions regarding the experiment observe photon 2.

The Variable: The “Idea” Conflict

At Station B, the two diametrically opposed professionals observe the results of photon 2:

- The Materialist Observer, **falsely informed** that the entanglement link has been broken, *expects* a 50/50 random (chaos) distribution of polarizations, as per the Born Rule.
- The Idealist Observer, **correctly informed** that the particles are entangled, *expects* a 100% correlation (order) of polarization between the photons.

The Measurement

- **The ISA Prediction:** The ill-informed Materialist’s expectation of “randomness” will cause the entangled correlation to degrade or disappear *only when they are looking*. This would be the “smoking gun” of ideas and their agency.
- **Standard Physics Prediction:** The particles are entangled regardless of what the observers think or expect, and that random results will always follow the Born Rule
- **The Falsification of Materialism:** If the data changes based upon what the materialist expects, then the “causal closure” of the physical world is broken and both Hypotheses are supported.
If the data doesn’t change, ISA's model of abstract agency is falsified.

Protocol 14. Ideas of Specific Agency

Geometric Intent - a refined version of Protocol 13: Immaterial realities (V-Rep, Ideas, unmeasured grains) can resonate and collapse to the quantum state of a physical or abstract object (ρ_{MIND}), though, a vague idea will only produce a vague result. To maximize “resonance” (p. 10) between the intentional mind and the resulting quantum state, the Vibrational Representation, the “idea” in the observer's head, needs to be as precise as a laser, so a more specific, highly-structured V-Rep is provided.

Hypothesis 1. Specific evolutionary ideas—V-Ideas, V-Reps can have agency.

The testable claim of both hypotheses:

The wave function is not collapsed by mechanical measurement alone. Collapse can also be triggered by the conceptual intent (specific idea) of an observer. Therefore, an observer holding a specific (non-random) idea (a V-Rep) can exert a measurable, statistical bias on quantum outcomes that contradict the standard physical probability of the Born Rule.

1. The Variable: a specific Idea of geometric intent

Instead of just “expecting” a result, the observers will hold the V-Rep of a specific geometric form in their mind. This will test if the structure of an idea can influence the distribution of discrete matter on the screen.

The Test: A specific idea attempts to override a well-established physical probability.

The Physical Setup:

- A double-slit experiment generates a flow of single electrons.
- The **Materialist** will focus on the standard idea of vertical strips, the “interference pattern.”
- The **Idealist** will focus on a divergent idea, for example, a **circular vortex**: the idealist will be trained to hold the abstract mathematical concept of a circle in their mind as they “observe” the electron hits.
- **The Prediction:** If the electron hits on the screen should begin to cluster in a way that defies the standard interference pattern and suggests a circular bias, the circular vortex, then the intentional idea is **real** and such ideas possess **agency**.

2. Eliminating the “physical interaction” excuse:

To eliminate the claim that the unusual circular vortex is just heat from the observer's body, we will use delayed feedback:

- The electrons hit the detector and the data is encrypted; no one sees the result.
- The observers interact with the encrypted file using their intent and expectation.
- Only *after* the period of mental “resonance” is the file decrypted.

Why this matters: If the data changes to match the divergent, circular idea after it was already recorded but before it was consciously processed, it will have been proven that evolutionary ideas ([V-Ideas](#), [V-Reps](#)) are the final authority on what becomes “Real.” If the observer’s intention today can influence data recorded yesterday (recorded, but not yet seen), it supports the notion that reality is an arrow of causality, and not an arrow of time. ^{4 (article)}

Falsification Criteria:

- If a highly trained observer's specific geometric idea (V-Rep) consistently *fails* to shift the probability distribution of quantum outcomes beyond the margin of experimental error—in a double-blind, delayed-choice environment—then the agency of specific ideas is falsified and Hypothesis 1 is not supported.
- If the circular-vortex bias appears only in real-time observation conditions and not in the delayed-feedback condition (where data was recorded but not yet seen), then the effect is attributable to a physical interaction between observer and apparatus, and the “arrow of causality” interpretation is falsified.

The following experiments produced results that remain anomalous within their original frameworks. ISA offers a parsimonious reinterpretation of each.

Protocol 15. The Libet Experiment

A Reinterpretation: The evolutionary process of CC&E could be a more robust way to explain the “gap” in Benjamin Libet’s 1983 experiment. This part of the experiment is known as the “Readiness Potential;” an evolutionary process gap of about 300 milliseconds. According to ISA and the recursive cognitive process of CC&E, all completed thoughts require a bodily feeling to provide significance. The production of this feeling occurs during the “interoceptive loop” during cycles of CC&E (p. 9, [Protocols 11 & 12](#)). The resultant thought of significance (the V-Rep) must occur before the subject can become aware of their intention of action. In this way, ISA explains the RP signal that the experiment is recording is, in fact, the actions of our body’s interoceptive system prior to awareness. That is, we revise and remap the experiment’s 300ms delay (the “RP”) in brain activity not as a materialist pre-determination, but as the evolutionary processing time required for preparation of the abstract action of intent before its emergence as a neural firing.

Protocol 16. The Hodgkin-Huxley Experiment

A Reinterpretation: As a single agent for coherently-grouped objects, the V-Idea of [Protocol 7](#) could be a more robust way to explain the anomalous opening, or state-change behavior of ion channels along neural tissue; specifically, their coordinated configuration and seemingly instantaneous state-changes along neural tissue as first observed by Hodgkin and Huxley (1952) in giant squid axons. What is the mechanism which governs the anomalous behavior and speed of these coherently-grouped ion channel state-changes? According to ISA, the system of ion channels is a *single* coherent object governed by a single V-Idea. Like a *pair* of entangled particles, a *bait ball* of sardines, or an *exaltation* of larks, a single V-Idea of the grouped ion channels evolves them as a *single* coherent system in each moment, at any speed, in any configuration, and over any distance from the abstract background. [Protocol 16](#) tests whether this singular grouped governance is real and measurable in a synthetic membrane preparation.

- **Hypothesis 1:** The system of ion channels along a membrane is a single coherently-grouped object, governed by a single parent V-Idea in the abstract background.
- **The Objective:** To detect simultaneity of ion channel state-changes across a synthetic membrane preparation at speeds which are inconsistent with classical propagation, in a manner which is consistent with ISA's V-Idea governance model of coherently-grouped objects ([Protocol 7](#)).

- **The Setup:** An artificial lipid bilayer membrane with reconstituted ion channels—a standard synthetic laboratory preparation requiring no animal subjects. Individual channels are monitored at spatially separated sites across the membrane. The preparation represents the parent V-Idea's domain; its individual ion channels are the “peer” members of the coherently-grouped object, each governed simultaneously by the single parent V-Idea.
- **The Procedure:** Apply a global stimulus—electrical or chemical—to the parent membrane system. Monitor individual ion channels for simultaneity of state-change using patch-clamp electrophysiology at multiple sites. Establish the classical propagation baseline:

$$\tau_{\text{CLASSICAL}} = d / V_{\text{SIGNAL}}$$

where d is the distance between monitored channel sites and V_{SIGNAL} is the classical electrochemical propagation speed through the membrane preparation.

- **Standard Physics Prediction:** Ion channel state-changes will propagate sequentially across the membrane at $\tau_{\text{CLASSICAL}}$, consistent with classical electrochemical signal transmission.
- **ISA Prediction:** Ion channel state-changes will occur simultaneously—or within a window far shorter than $\tau_{\text{CLASSICAL}}$ because they are governed not by classical signal propagation but by a single parent V-Idea acting from the abstract background. The simultaneity will be proportional and coordinated, consistent with the coherently-grouped model of [Protocol 7](#), not random.

Formalism: The coherent grouping synchronization condition applies directly:

$$f_1 \approx f_2 \approx \dots \approx f_n \approx f_{\text{GROUP}}$$

The critical measurable distinction remains the timing:

$$\tau_{\text{ISA}} < \hbar / E_{\text{BW}}$$

where E_{BW} is the bandwidth energy of the parent membrane system ([Protocol 5](#)). If the observed simultaneity satisfies $\tau_{\text{OBSERVED}} \ll \tau_{\text{CLASSICAL}}$, the coherently-grouped V-Idea model is supported.

Unlike Orch-OR's proposed mechanism for the anomalous state-changes, which requires quantum coherence to survive the warm, wet neural environment—a requirement challenged by Tegmark's decoherence calculations (2000)—ISA's V-Idea operates from the abstract background and is therefore immune to thermal decoherence entirely. The synthetic membrane preparation additionally eliminates biological variability, providing the cleanest possible test of coherently-grouped V-Idea governance independent of the complexities of living neural tissue.

- **Falsification:** If ion channel state-changes propagate sequentially at intervals consistent with $\tau_{\text{CLASSICAL}}$ —that is, if the classical electrochemical cascade fully accounts for the observed coordination—the V-Idea model of ion channel governance as a coherently-grouped object is falsified.

Appendix: the measurement-collapse problem

What determines the duration of the static moment; the evolutionary process before an object's emergence? This question has usually been framed as, What determines the "collapse" of the Schrödinger wave function? According to ISA, the duration of the evolutionary process is determined by several knowable factors . . . which do not violate the uncertainty principle since they only help to determine the "when" of collapse, and not the "where." The factors are:

- **Shared "Bandwidth"** - an object's speed through Space and Time:
According to this model, moving time **is** the evolutionary process of CC&E. Compatible with role the model is special relativity in which objects always maintain a motion through space and through time (CC&E) which is equivalent to the speed of light, **c**. In this way, the motion of an object's evolutionary rate must decrease as motion of its positional change in spacetime ("motion through space") increases. In other words, there exists a shared bandwidth of total energy through space and through time which is always maintained at **c**; a bandwidth which limits all of an object's motions, both discrete and abstract. See Time paper, Protocol 5.
- **Gravity:** - the inherent motion of a "conditioned" space:
Just like motion through space, above, the evolution of an object within a gravitational field will also affect the duration its evolutionary process (time) as per special relativity, though, within the model, the force called "gravity" occurs by means of "conditioned," that is, grains of accelerated space. For a fuller explanation, please see my article, *Gravity, The Idea of Motion*, at Medium.com. See also, Time paper, Protocol 6.
- **"Nesting"** - objects evolve in concert with each other:
The evolutionary process of an object is affected by the needs of other objects within it's "nest." This, in turn, affects the duration of the object's evolutionary process. A particle, for example, evolves according to its vibrational idea (V-Idea), but only after its measured values have been constrained by the V-Idea of the larger object to which it belongs. That is, the measured property values of a particle belonging to a coherent object are constrained by the measured values of the atom to which it belongs which, in turn, is constrained by the molecule, the atom, the protein, and so on with the universe as a whole is technically the outermost nest, but its V-Idea imposes only the broadest constraints (essentially, the laws of nature), leaving enormous freedom to the inner nests. In practice, the relevant nest is determined by causal proximity and the boundary of the coherent object in question. As an example of the largest of nests, the V-Idea of your brain sets an operational range of measured particle property values for the V-Ideas of its constituent components all the way down to those of its particles so that they will evolve properly as your coherently functioning brain here in spacetime. See also, [Protocol 8](#).
- **The Observer Effect:** - the agency of the abstract background:
This well-known phenomenon should also affect the duration of an object's evolutionary process time. According to the model, the observer effect is, essentially, the *blending action* of

three defined abstractions with specific informational structures—the observer’s V-Idea and V-Rep, and the unmeasured values of the grain—undergo a particular process with a measurable physical result. In the simplest experimental case, this may be the blending of a particle’s V-Idea as it travels through the experiment’s obstacle course with an observer’s expectant or intentional idea of “which path” information, resulting in the fate of the particle to either a discrete or abstract form. In the cases of general evolutionary and cognitive processes, it is essentially the mechanism of observation which brings about the reality of objects both material and abstract. For a fuller description of the Observer Effect, please see For Further Reading; The Delayed Choice Quantum Eraser.

- **Cosmic Expansion:** - a measurement problem of a different sort:
Cosmic expansion may also affect the duration of an object’s static moment as it evolves in grains of space which may be expanding through its “location.” The idea of “locations **in** space” implies locations with co-ordinates within a larger field of spacetime when, in fact, these tiny grains **are** the spacetime, with positions which are relative only to each other (the “locations”). While it is now clear that the cosmos is expanding, no one is yet sure of the rate of expansion, such that it may not yet be possible to precisely calculate the effect of this motion upon the evolutionary process.

The incorporation of the above factors into the Schrödinger equation may yield a more precise calculation of an object’s evolutionary duration, and hence, its collapse. In this way, the “measurement problem” isn’t a glitch in physics. Rather, it’s a resource management issue of shared bandwidth. If the process of CC&E is the motion of moving time, then all of its actions (speed, gravity, observation, expansion, collisions, and other nested interactions) consume a portion of that evolutionary bandwidth. According to the uncertainty principle, a precise calculation of duration and collapse is allowed since, without information of precisely *where* collapse will occur, nothing is violated.

Notes

1. This paper falls within the larger, “parent” theory of Inter-Spatial Abstraction. For more on ISA, please see the most recent book edition of *Between Space* (in preparation).
2. Because space is quantized into grains and particles, they have no location **within** space since they **are** the only space there is. Likewise, there’s no “location” within the background, a timeless, spaceless domain of abstraction between grains. Rather, while we will use the word “location” for convenience, there is only the “relative position” of grains and parties to each other. Similarly, there is no “motion **through** space” or “speed **through** space” since particles and grains do not move through each other. And so, while we will use these expressions for convenience, there is only a frequency and rate of emergence which we misunderstand as “motion” and “speed.”
3. Which came first? The chicken or the egg? The problem of a circular causation here between the initial establishment of both the grain and the V-Idea would be avoided if the discrete spacetime of particles would be an emergent manifestation of the more primary background of awareness. In this way, the primacy of a universal awareness—the abstract background—would somehow puff out grains of unmeasured particle property value to “get things going.” Through the initial observation of measured values upon a few grains on the part of awareness, the grains would collapse to discrete particles which would then be noticed by and updated to a new evolutionary function of the background—the vibrational ideas—as the ongoing agents in the evolutionary process of CC&E.
4. “. . . evolves its particle **as** a static moment . . .” rather than **in** a static moment.
For a fuller explanation, please see my earlier paper, *A New Model of Time*.
5. While the Schrödinger equation can describe the evolutionary process of a particle, it does not resolve the measurement problem; what causes a grain to collapse to the discrete form of a particle? Perhaps the disappointingly obvious explanation is that the duration of a particle’s emergence, or state of being is determined by the time required by its evolutionary process of CC&E, and that the condensation, or collapse of the particle occurs only when the abstract, unmeasured properties of the grain have attained measured values through that process. (pp. 5, 21, 22)
6. That is, some fraction of a “second” only *in relation* to the static moments of some time keeping device and not *according to* some external temporal mechanism. This will become important later.
7. Hameroff and Penrose (Orch-OR Theory, 2014) similarly propose the microtubule network as central to consciousness, invoking quantum coherence to account for the anomalous speed of ion-channel propagation first described in Hodgkin and Huxley’s work with squid neurons (1952). ISA offers an alternative explanation: The V-Idea of the MTN evolves ion-channel activity from the abstract background (p. 3, 5) without requiring physical quantum coherence to survive the warm, wet neural environment, additionally avoiding Tegmark’s objection (2000) that the duration of thermal decoherence in biological tissue is far too short for the mechanism of Orch-OR to operate as proposed.
8. The two-step thought process in this model’s description of consciousness would account for the “gap” between the ‘readiness potential’ and ‘decision to act’ in Benjamin Libet’s experiment (1983): ISA explains that (step 1) a *rational* meaning of a stimulation brings about bodily (interoceptive) motions before (step 2) the acquisition of the *irrational* meaning, or emotion is brought about which completes the experience. Also, contrary to the conclusion of pre-determinism by some, cognition seems to originate freely through the two-step process of moving time and the blending of random ideas of most likely resonance (p. 10).
Interoceptive feeling is also an important component of Antonio Damasio’s somatic marker hypothesis which identifies body-to-brain interoceptive feedback as the source of emotional significance in cognition.
ISA’s dualist description of consciousness differs fundamentally; it locates the significance-generating step in the abstract background rather than in the materialism of somatic markers alone.
9. In this way, it turns out that the microtubule network is the NCC, or neural correlate of consciousness.
10. While “experience” is the number of ideas which your mind has acquired, “wisdom” might be a measure of their increasing complexity and significance.
11. See Thomas Nagel (1974).
12. For a more detailed description of gravity, please see:
<https://garyblaise.medium.com/gravity-the-idea-of-motion-9ae6935057d0>

Citations

Hameroff, Stuart and Penrose, Roger. (2014). Consciousness in the universe: A review of the "Orch OR" theory. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 11(1), 39–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2013.08.002>

Hameroff, Stuart, ion channel propagation, TSC 2023, Youtube @ 12 minutes

Hodgkin, A. L. & Huxley, A. F. (1952). A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve. *The Journal of Physiology*, 117(4), 500–544. doi:10.1113/jphysiol.1952.sp004764

Tegmark, Max (2000). The importance of quantum decoherence in brain processes. *Physical Review E*, 61(4), 4194–4206. doi.org

Libet, Benjamin, Gleason, C. A., Wright, E. W., & Pearl, D. K. (1983). “Time of conscious intention to act in relation to onset of cerebral activity (readiness-potential): The unconscious initiation of a freely voluntary act.” *Brain*, 106(3), 623–642. doi.org

Damasio, A.R.; Tranel, D.; Damasio, H.C. (1991). "Ch. 11: Somatic markers and the guidance of behaviour: theory and preliminary testing". In Levin, Harvey S.; Eisenberg, Howard M.; Benton, Arthur Lester (eds.). *Frontal Lobe Function and Dysfunction*. Oxford University Press. pp. 217–229. ISBN 978-0-19-506284-7.

Nagel, Thomas, “What Is It Like to Be a Bat?”, *The Philosophical Review*, Vol. 83, No. 4. (Oct., 1974), pp. 435-450

For Further Reading

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For a fuller explanation of the Observer Effect, please see The Delayed Choice Quantum Eraser Experiment: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delayed-choice_quantum_eraser

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